

2.63 δ (1H) and 2.77 δ (1H) were attributed to the two benzylic protons. The C-3 and C-4 protons of the coumarinic lactone ring appeared as doublet centered at 6.17 δ (1H, $J = 9.5$ Hz) and at 7.56 δ

(1H, $J = 9.5$ Hz). The C-8 and C-5 aromatic protons appeared as sharp singlets at 6.72 δ (1H) and 7.16 δ (1H) respectively. The six methylene and one methine protons appeared as broad multiplet centered at 1.62 δ . Thus the NMR data is fully in accord with the structure (II) proposed for the cyclized product.

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Chemical Examination of the Leaves of *Careya arborea*

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ISOLATION of a number of triterpenes have been reported earlier from the leaves of *Careya arborea*¹⁻⁴. The present communication reports the isolation of valoneic acid dilactone from the leaves

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of the same plant. It was however isolated as its methylated derivative as the acid itself was found to be susceptible to aerial oxidation.

The ether insoluble part of the ethanolic extract of the leaves was hydrolysed with 5% ethanolic hydrochloric acid. The sapogenin thus obtained was extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with solvent ether for 24 hr. During this extraction a white solid precipitated out. It was filtered and found to be sparingly soluble in most common organic solvents, like benzene, ether, chloroform etc. and it turned dark on heating on a steam bath. So the material was suspended in a large volume of ethyl acetate and treated with ethereal diazomethane. On working up followed by purification by column chromatography a crystalline solid, $C_{28}H_{24}O_{13}$ (Ia, M^+ 568), m.p. 258°-62° (dec.), $\lambda_{max}^{CHCl_3}$ 367, 352, 295 and 251 nm, was obtained. This was found to be homogeneous on TLC.

Its IR spectrum ($CHCl_3$) showed bands at 1745 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl) and 1730 cm^{-1} (carbomethoxyl group). The bands at 1607 cm^{-1} and 1575 cm^{-1} were due to aromatic ring. Its mass spectral fragmentation pattern was commensurate with the structure (Ia).

It showed strong peaks at m/e 343, m/e 327, m/e 241 and m/e 225 all arising out of cleavage of the ether linkage. The intense peak at m/e 211 was due to the ion a.

The NMR spectrum of (Ia) (60 MHz, $CDCl_3$) showed sharp singlets at 3.80 δ (3H), 3.95 δ (6H), 4.05 δ (3H), 4.2 δ (3H) and 4.3 δ (3H) for the eighteen protons of the six methoxyl groups. The three protons of the carbomethoxyl group appeared as a singlet at 3.75 δ . The three aromatic protons at C-3 (ring A), C-3 (ring C) and at C-3 (ring B), appeared as singlets at 7.2 δ (1H), 7.3 δ (1H) and 7.65 δ (1H), respectively. The downfieldship of the proton at C-3 (ring B) is most probably due to the proximity of the lactone carbonyl on one hand and the oxygen of the ether linkage on the other hand.

The methylated product on saponification furnished an acid which was crystallized from methanol, $C_{27}H_{22}O_{13}$ (Ib, M^+ 554), m.p. 273°-76°. Its IR spectrum (Nujol mull) showed bands at 1745 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl), 1712 cm^{-1} (carboxyl group), 1607 cm^{-1} and 1575 cm^{-1} (aromatic rings). The acid (Ib) on ethylation with ethereal diazoethane furnished (Ic), $C_{29}H_{26}O_{13}$, m.p. 290-94° (dec.). Its NMR spectrum (60 MHz, pyridine) showed sharp singlets at 3.92 δ (3H), 3.95 δ (6H), 4.05 δ (3H), 4.22 δ

(3H) and 4.48 δ (3H) for the eighteen protons of the six methoxyl groups. There was a triplet centered at 1.22 δ (3H, $J = 7$ Hz) for the methyl protons of the carboethoxyl group ($-\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$) and a quartet centered at 4.30 δ (2H, $J = 7$ Hz) for the methylene protons of the carboethoxyl group ($-\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$). The change in the chemical shift in the above spectrum was due to the solvent (Pyridine). As (Ic) was insoluble in CHCl_3 and CDCl_3 its NMR spectrum was carried out in pyridine.

Thus all the above data clearly indicated that the methylated product has the structure (Ia). In 1965 Schmidt⁵ *et al.* reported from *Quercus valonea* and *Q. macrolepis* the isolation of valoneic acid dilactone (Id) which formed a hexamethyl ether methyl ester (Ia). Although no direct comparison with authentic sample of hexamethyl ether of valoneic acid dilactone methyl ester has been possible there appears to be very little doubt that our methylated product is identical with hexamethyl ether of valoneic acid dilactone methyl ester. So it appears likely that the original polyhydroxy aromatic acid obtained from the leaves of *C. arborea* is valoneic acid dilactone although the possibility of the original acid being a partially methylated valoneic acid dilactone cannot be completely overruled.

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Mercuric Acetate as an Initiator of Vinyl Polymerization

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THE effects of metal salts on polymerization reactions are very diverse depending on the type of metal ion, the associated anion, the nature of monomer

and probably the medium in which the reaction is carried out. Spontaneous initiation of certain vinyl monomers by metal salts is reported by several workers¹⁻⁵.

Thus the examples of vinyl polymerization initiated by inorganic salts alone are not rare, but practically no evidence is available where mercuric acetate acts as an initiator of polymerization. While working on the effect of metal salts we observed that mercuric acetate can initiate polymerization of certain vinyl monomers. Attempts were made to study the kinetics of MMA-HgAc₂ system in DMF at 60° but unfortunately the results were not strictly reproducible. We however made some preliminary observations and tried to suggest a mechanism of polymerization. The observations included the study of the following: (1) monomer selectivity, (2) effect of solvent and (3) nature of reaction.

Monomer selectivity

Methylmethacrylate, styrene and acrylonitrile were successfully polymerized in DMF at 60° in the absence of oxygen using mercuric acetate (1×10^{-2} moles/lit) as an initiator; but in the case of acrylamide only initiation was observed under identical conditions.

Effect of solvent

Various solvents were used as the polymerization medium in the case of mercuric acetate initiated polymerization of methylmethacrylate at 60°. A measurable amount of polymer was obtained when the reaction was carried out in the solvents like DMF, formamide, *n*-butylamine and formic acid. But polymerization was not effected in solvents such as, acetonitrile, pyridine or alcohol. In all the cases the polymerization was homogeneous but in the case of formic acid blackish precipitation was found and this may be the precipitation of $\text{Hg}(\text{OOCH})_2$ or metallic mercury.

Nature of reaction

The polymerization of methylmethacrylate initiated by mercuric acetate in DMF at 60° was inhibited by both the diphenyl-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) and *p*-benzoquinone. This suggests that probably free radical mechanism is operative in this case. This was further confirmed by co-polymer (MMA+styrene) analysis spectrophotometrically using the technique of Tobolsky *et al.*⁶ The principle of the method is that unlike polystyrene, poly-methylmethacrylate is optically clear above 250 nm in chloroform. So a copolymer of methylmethacrylate and styrene having different feed ratio was prepared at 60° in DMF using 1.13×10^{-3} mole/lit mercuric acetate as initiator. The polymer after rigorous purification by usual method was dried at 40° in an oven for 12 hr. Exactly 0.1% polymer solution in chloroform was made and optical density was measured using a Hilger Spectrophotometer at 269 nm. From the calibration curve⁶ percent of styrene in the copolymer at different

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